

UNIQUENESS OF A MEROMORPHIC FUNCTION AND ITS LINEAR DIFFERENTIAL POLYNOMIAL SHARING VALUES WITH SOME WEIGHTS

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Abstract:

In this paper, we investigate the uniqueness problem of meromorphic functions and the linear differential polynomial associated with them from the point of view of sharing a values. In the meantime, the findings that were acquired through the use of this paper generalise the findings of A. Banerjee and A. Kundu[1].

Keywords: Meromorphic functions, differential polynomials, small functions, sharing values.

Subject Classification: 30D35

1. INTRODUCTION AND DEFINITIONS

Within the context of this paper, "entire function" denotes that the function is analytic everywhere in $\mathbb{C}$. The Nevanlinna Theory's basic fundamentals can be found in [5]. We represent $E = \{x: x \in \mathbb{R}^+\}$ whose linear measure is finite. Let F be the set of all non-constant entire functions in the complex plane. For any two functions f and g belonging to the set F , and $a \in \mathbb{C} \cup \{\infty\}$, if the zeros of $f - a$ and $g - a$ are exactly the same, including their multiplicities, then f and g share a with counting multiplicities (CM). If the multiplicities are not taken into account, then f and g have a common zero ignoring multiplicities (IM). Furthermore if $\frac{1}{f}$ and $\frac{1}{g}$ share 0 CM, then f and g share ∞ CM.

Readers are assumed to be familiar with the fundamentals of Nevanlinna's value distribution theory of meromorphic functions in $\mathbb{C}$, including the first and second main theorems, standard notations, and the counting functions $N(r, \infty; f)$ (Counting multiplicity), $\bar{N}(r, \infty; f)$ (ignoring multiplicity), the proximity function $m(r, f)$ and $T(r, \infty; f)$ (characteristic function).

Definition 1.1 [8] Let k be a non-negative integer or infinity. For $a \in \mathbb{C} \cup \{\infty\}$, we denote $E_k(a; f)$ the set of all a points of f , where an a point of multiplicity m is counted m times if $m \leq k$ and $k + 1$ times if $m > k$. If $E_k(a; f) = E_k(a; g)$ then f, g share a with weight k .

If $f - a$ and $g - a$ both share $(0, k)$, then they also share $(0, p)$ in common for any value of $0 \leq p < k$. Additionally, it should be observed that $f - a$ and $g - a$ share the value of 0 IM or CM if and only if $f - a$ and $g - a$ share $(0, 0)$ or $(0, \infty)$, respectively.

Definition 1.2 For a non-constant meromorphic function f , the set of all small functions of f is denoted by $S(f)$, i.e., $S(f) = \{a \in M(\mathbb{C}): T(r, a) = S(r, f) \text{ as } r \rightarrow \infty\}$. Clearly $S(f) \subset M(\mathbb{C})$.

Now we present the following definitions, which were first introduced by I. Lahiri.

Definition 1.3 [6] Let $a \in S(f)$, by $N\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a} \mid \geq s\right) \left(N\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a} \mid \leq s\right)\right)$ we denote the counting function of those zeros of $f - a$ of multiplicity $\geq s$ ($\leq s$). Also $\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a} \mid \geq s\right) \left(\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a} \mid \leq s\right)\right)$ are defined analogously.

Definition 1.4 [7] Consider two non-constant meromorphic functions, f and g such that both $f - a$ and $g - a$ share $(0,0)$. Consider z_0 is a zero of $f - a$ with multiplicity of p , and also a zero of $g - a$ with a multiplicity of q . $\bar{N}_L\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right)$ is represented by the reduced counting function of those zeros of $f - a$ and $g - a$, where $p > q$. Similarly by $\bar{N}_L\left(r, \frac{1}{g-a}\right)$ the reduced counting function of those zeros of $f - a$ and $g - a$, where $p < q$.

Also by $\bar{N}_*\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}; \frac{1}{g-a}\right)$ the reduced counting function of those zeros of $f - a$ and $g - a$, where $p \neq q$ and clearly $\bar{N}_*\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}; \frac{1}{g-a}\right) = \bar{N}_L\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + \bar{N}_L\left(r, \frac{1}{g-a}\right)$.

Let us consider $f - a$ and $g - a$ share 0 . Then by $N_{(m,n)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right)\left(\bar{N}_{(m,n)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right)\right)$ we represent the counting (reduced counting) function refers to the number of zeros of $f - a$ and $g - a$, where these zeros have multiplicity m and n respectively.

The following is the definition of a linear differential polynomial:

$$L(f) = \sum_{i=0}^k (a_i f^{(i)}) = a_0(f) + a_1 f' + a_2 f'' + \dots + a_k f^{(k)}, \quad (1.1)$$

where $f^{(i)}$ is the i^{th} derivative of f and a_i 's are small functions of f .

In 2023, A. Banerjee and Arpita Kundu[1] proved the following result.

Theorem A Let f be a non-constant transcendental meromorphic function, and a, b be two distinct small functions, k be a positive integer. If $f - a$ and $f^{(k)} - a$ share $(0, \infty)$ and $f - b$ and $f^{(k)} - b$ share $(0,0)$ and $\bar{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$ and $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{1}{22k+20}\right]$, then $f \equiv f^{(k)}$.

Theorem B Let f be a non-constant meromorphic function, and a, b be two distinct small functions, k be a positive integer. If $f - a$ and $f^{(k)} - a$ share $(0,1)$ and $f - b$ and $f^{(k)} - b$ share $(0,1)$ and $\bar{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$ where $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{1}{4k+5}\right]$, then $f \equiv f^{(k)}$.

Theorem C Let f be a non-constant meromorphic function, and a, b be two distinct small functions, k be a positive integer. If $f - a$ and $f^{(k)} - a$ share $(0,1)$ and $f - b$ and $f^{(k)} - b$ share $(0,0)$ and $\bar{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$ and $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{1}{8k^2+36k+31}\right]$, then $f \equiv f^{(k)}$.

Theorem D Let f be a non-constant meromorphic function, and b be a small function of f , k be a positive integer. If f and $f^{(k)}$ share $(0, \infty)$ and $f - b$ and $f^{(k)} - b$ share $(0,0)$ and satisfies $\bar{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$ where $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{1}{k+1}\right]$, then $f \equiv f^{(k)}$.

Theorem E Let f be a non-constant meromorphic function, and b be a small function of f , and $k (> 1)$ be a positive integer. If f and $f^{(k)}$ share $(0, k)$ and $f - b$ and $f^{(k)} - b$ share $(0,1)$ and satisfies $\bar{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$, where $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{k-1}{(k+1)^2}\right]$, then $f \equiv f^{(k)}$.

Theorem F Let f be a non-constant meromorphic function, b be a small function of f , k be a positive integer. If $f, f^{(k)}$ share $(0, k)$, $f - b$ and $f^{(k)} - b$ share $(0,0)$ and satisfies $\bar{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$ where $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{k}{2k^2+3k+1}\right]$, then $f \equiv f^{(k)}$.

Theorem G Let f be a non-constant meromorphic function, and a, b be two distinct non-zero rational small functions of f , k be a positive integer. If $f - a$ and $f^{(k)} - a$ share $(0, k)$ and $f - b$ and $f^{(k)} - b$ share $(0, k)$ and satisfies $\overline{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$, where $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{1}{2k+3}\right]$, then $f \equiv f^{(k)}$.

Theorem H Let f be a non-constant meromorphic function, and a, b be two distinct small functions, k be a positive integer. If $f - a$ and $f^{(k)} - a$ share $(0, \infty)$ and $f - b$ and $f^{(k)} - b$ share $(0, 0)$ and $N(r, f) = S(r, f)$, then $f \equiv f^{(k)}$.

We have investigated uniqueness of f and a linear differential polynomial sharing two values a and b with weight k . Clearly here Theorems 1.1 to 1.7 improves the Theorems A to G.

Theorem 1.1 Let a, b be two different values $\in \mathbb{C}$, k be a positive integer, and f be a non-constant transcendental meromorphic function. $\overline{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$ and $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{1}{22k+20}\right]$. If $f - a$ and $L(f) - a$ share $(0, \infty)$ and $f - b$ and $L(f) - b$ share $(0, 0)$, then $f \equiv L(f)$.

Theorem 1.2 Assume that k is a positive integer, a, b are two different values that lie within $\mathbb{C}$, and f is a non-constant meromorphic function. If $f - a$ and $L(f) - a$ share $(0, 1)$ and $f - b$ and $L(f) - b$ share $(0, 1)$ and $\overline{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$ where $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{1}{4k+5}\right]$, then $f \equiv L(f)$.

Theorem 1.3 Consider a non-constant meromorphic function, denoted by f , and let a and b be two distinct values $\in \mathbb{C}$. Let k be a positive integer. If $f - a$ and $L(f) - a$ share $(0, 1)$, $f - b$ and $L(f) - b$ share $(0, 0)$, $\overline{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$ and $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{1}{8k^2+36k+31}\right]$, then $f \equiv L(f)$.

Theorem 1.4 Let k be a positive integer, $b \in \mathbb{C}$, and f be a non-constant meromorphic function. $\overline{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$ where $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{1}{k+1}\right]$ is satisfied, $f \equiv L(f)$ if f and $L(f)$ share $(0, \infty)$ and $f - b$ and $L(f) - b$ share $(0, 0)$.

Theorem 1.5 Let's say that $b \in \mathbb{C}$, and $k (> 1)$ be positive integers, and that f is a non-constant meromorphic function. $\overline{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$, where $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{k-1}{(k+1)^2}\right]$, is satisfied. If f and $L(f)$ share $(0, k)$ and $f - b$ and $L(f) - b$ share $(0, 1)$. Consequently, $f \equiv L(f)$.

Theorem 1.6 Let $b \in \mathbb{C}$, k be a positive integer, and f be a non-constant meromorphic function. When f and $L(f)$ share $(0, k)$, $f - b$ and $L(f) - b$ share $(0, 0)$ and $\overline{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$ where $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{k}{2k^2+3k+1}\right]$, then $f \equiv L(f)$.

Theorem 1.7 Let a, b be two distinct non-zero rational small functions of f , and let k be a positive integer. Let f be a non-constant meromorphic function. $\overline{N}(r, f) < \lambda T(r, f)$ where $\lambda \in \left[0, \frac{1}{2k+3}\right]$ is satisfied, and $f \equiv L(f)$ if $f - a$ and $L(f) - a$ share $(0, k)$ and $f - b$ and $L(f) - b$ share $(0, k)$.

2. LEMMAS

In order to prove our findings, we require the following lemmas.

Lemma 2.1 [10], Consider a non-constant meromorphic function $f(z)$, where a and b are two distinct small functions of f , with $a \neq \infty$ and $b \neq \infty$. Set

$$\Delta(f) = \begin{vmatrix} f - a & b - a \\ f' - a' & b' - a' \end{vmatrix}$$

and

$$\Delta(L(f)) = \begin{vmatrix} L(f) - a & b - a \\ L(f)' - a' & b' - a' \end{vmatrix}.$$

Subsequently, we can possess,

- i. $\Delta(f) \neq 0$ and $\Delta(L(f)) \neq 0$,
- ii. $m\left(r, \frac{\Delta(f)}{(f-a)(f-b)}\right) = S(r, f)$, $m\left(r, \frac{\Delta(L(f))}{(L(f)-a)(L(f)-b)}\right) = S(r, f)$,
- iii. $m\left(r, \frac{\Delta(f)}{f-a}\right) = S(r, f)$, $m\left(r, \frac{\Delta(f)}{f-b}\right) = S(r, f)$,
- iv. $m\left(r, \frac{\Delta(L(f))}{L(f)-a}\right) = S(r, f)$, $m\left(r, \frac{\Delta(L(f))}{L(f)-b}\right) = S(r, f)$.

Lemma 2.2 [1], Considering a small function a , and a non-constant transcendental meromorphic function $f(z)$, let denote f . If $f - a, L(f) - a$ share $(0, \infty)$, $N\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a}\right) \leq (9k + 3)\bar{N}(r, f)$ and $a \not\equiv a^{(k)}$, then either

$$T(r, L(f)) \leq (11k + 3)\bar{N}(r, f) \text{ or } (f - a) = h_e(L(f) - a), \text{ where } T(r, h_e) = S(r, f).$$

Proof of the Lemma 2.2 Given that f and $L(f)$ share a CM, there exist an entire function h_e such that

$$h_e = \frac{f-a}{L(f)-a}. \tag{2.1}$$

Obviously,

$$f - a = h_e(L(f) - a) = h_e(L(f) - a^{(k)}) - h_e(a - a^{(k)}). \tag{2.2}$$

Differentiating (2.2) k time, setting up $P = L(f) - a^{(k)}$ and taking $b = a - a^{(k)}$, where $g = f^{(k)} - a^{(k)}$ we possess

$$g = (h_e P)^{(k)} - (h_e b)^{(k)} \tag{2.3}$$

Let us set the functions as $G = g$, $H = \frac{(h_e P)^{(k)}}{h_e P}$ and $C = \frac{(h_e b)^{(k)}}{h_e}$ then from (2.3) we have

$$G = h_e(PH - C) \tag{2.4}$$

$$g = h_e \left(P \frac{(h_e P)^{(k)}}{h_e P} - \frac{(h_e b)^{(k)}}{h_e} \right)$$

Given that $G \not\equiv 0$, if $C \equiv 0$, then we can conclude that $h_e b = P_{k-1}$, where $P_{k-1} (\not\equiv 0)$ is a polynomial of degree $k - 1$. Consequently, $T\left(r, \frac{1}{h_e}\right) = S(r, f)$. If $H \equiv 0$, then we have $h_e P = P_{k-1}$ and this implies $N(r, P) = S(r, f)$. Applying the equation (2.3), we obtain

$$\frac{1}{h_e^2} = \frac{-1}{p_{k-1}} \cdot \frac{(h_e b)^{(k)}}{h_e}.$$

The implication here is that $m\left(r, \frac{1}{h_e}\right) = S(r, f)$ thus $T\left(r, \frac{1}{h_e}\right) = S(r, f)$.

Now, let's assume that none of the functions G, H , and C is equal to zero. We can express equation (2.4) as follows:

$$\frac{1}{h_e} = \frac{1}{G}(PH - C) = \frac{P}{G}H - \frac{C}{G}, \tag{2.5}$$

Differentiating (2.5) We possess

$$\frac{-h'_e}{h_e^2} = \frac{HP'}{G} - \frac{HPG'}{G^2} + \frac{P}{G}H' - \frac{C'}{G} + \frac{CG'}{G^2} \quad (2.6)$$

With (2.5) in (2.6), we obtain

$$\frac{I}{G} = \frac{HP'}{G} - \frac{HPG'}{G^2} + \frac{h'_ePH}{h_eG} + \frac{PH'}{G}, \quad (2.7)$$

where

$$I = \frac{Ch'_e}{h_e} + C' - \frac{CG'}{G}. \quad (2.8)$$

Case-1. $I \not\equiv 0$. By utilising equations (2.7) and (2.8), we find

$$m\left(r, \frac{1}{G}\right) \leq m\left(r, \frac{H}{I}\left(\frac{P'}{G} - \frac{PG'}{G^2} + \frac{h'_eP}{h_eG} + \frac{PH'}{GH}\right)\right) \quad (2.9)$$

$$\leq m(r, H) + m\left(r, \frac{1}{I}\right) + m\left(r, \frac{P'}{G}\right) + m\left(r, \frac{G'}{G}\right) + m\left(r, \frac{h'_e}{h_e}\right) + m\left(r, \frac{P}{G}\right) + m\left(r, \frac{H'}{H}\right).$$

Since $m\left(r, \frac{P'}{G}\right) = m\left(r, \frac{P}{G}\right) = k\bar{N}(r, f)$

$$\leq T(r, I) + (2k)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \leq N(r, I) + (2k)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f).$$

With reference to (2.9), we have

$$T(r, G) = T\left(r, \frac{1}{G}\right) = m\left(r, \frac{1}{G}\right) + N\left(r, \frac{1}{G}\right) \quad (2.10)$$

$$\leq N(r, I) + (2k)\bar{N}(r, f) + N\left(r, \frac{1}{G}\right) \leq (11k + 7)\bar{N}(r, f).$$

That is,

$$T(r, L(f)) \leq (11k + 7)\bar{N}(r, f).$$

Case-2. If $I \equiv 0$, therefore, based on equation (2.8), we can conclude that

$$\frac{h'_e}{h_e} + \frac{C'}{G} - \frac{G'}{G} = 0,$$

which on integration yields $(h_e b)^{(k)} = cg$ and this suggests $N(r, g) = S(r, f)$ and hence $N\left(r, \frac{1}{h_e}\right) = S(r, f)$. Now using $(h_e b)^{(k)} = cg$ in (2.3) we get

$$\frac{1}{h_e} = \frac{1}{1+c} \cdot \frac{(h_e g)^{(k)}}{h_e g}. \quad (2.11)$$

From (2.11) we are able to obtain $m\left(r, \frac{1}{h_e}\right) = S(r, f)$ and hence $T\left(r, \frac{1}{h_e}\right) = S(r, f)$. Additionally, we observe that $1 + c \neq 0$, alternatively, it signifies $H \equiv 0$.

Lemma 2.3 [1], Let $f = \sum_{i=1}^m (a_i h^i)$, where $T(r, a_i) = S(r, f)$ and h is a meromorphic function such that $h' = \eta h$, where $T(r, \eta) = S(r, f)$. Then $T(r, L(f)) = T(r, f) + S(r, f)$.

3. PROOF OF THEOREMS

Proof of Theorem 1.1 Initially, let us assume $f \not\equiv L(f)$. It is given that $f - a$ and $L(f) - a$ share $(0, \infty)$ and $f - b$ and $L(f) - b$ share $(0, 0)$. Let us denote the function

$$\kappa = \frac{L(f)-a}{f-a}. \quad (3.1)$$

Obviously κ has no zero and the only poles of κ come from the pole of f . By applying the second main theorem, we obtain

$$T(r, f) \leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) + \bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \quad (3.2)$$

thus,

$$T(r, f) \leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-b}\right) + \bar{N}(r, L(f)) + S(r, f) \quad (3.3)$$

$$\leq 3T(r, L(f)) + S(r, f).$$

Also,

$$T(r, L(f)) \leq T(r, f) + k\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \quad (3.4)$$

$$\leq (k+1)T(r, f) + S(r, f).$$

Thus, from (3.3), (3.4), we obtain $S(r, L(f)) = S(r, f)$. Next, introduce the following auxiliary function,

$$\phi = \frac{\Delta(f)(f-L(f))}{(f-a)(f-b)}, \quad (3.5)$$

$$\chi = \frac{\Delta(L(f))(f-L(f))}{(L(f)-a)(L(f)-b)}. \quad (3.6)$$

Clearly from (3.5) and (3.6) we have

$$T(r, \phi - \chi) = m(r, \phi - \chi) + N(r, \phi - \chi) \quad (3.7)$$

$$\leq m(r, \phi) + m(r, \chi) + (k+1)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f)$$

$$\leq m(r, \chi) + (k+1)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f),$$

and here,

$$m(r, \chi) \leq m\left(r, \frac{f-L(f)}{L(f)-a}\right) + S(r, f) \quad (3.8)$$

$$\leq m\left(r, \frac{f-a}{L(f)-a}\right) + N\left(r, \frac{f-a}{L(f)-a}\right) - N\left(r, \frac{f-a}{L(f)-a}\right) + S(r, f)$$

$$\leq T\left(r, \frac{L(f)-a}{f-a}\right) + S(r, f)$$

$$\leq T(r, \kappa) + S(r, f)$$

$$\leq m\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + N\left(r, \frac{L(f)-a}{f-a}\right) + S(r, f)$$

$$\leq m\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + k\bar{N}(r, f).$$

Case 1: Let $\phi - \chi \equiv 0$ and $f \not\equiv L(f)$. Then from $\phi - \chi \equiv 0$ we get

$$\frac{\Delta(f)}{(f-a)(f-b)} = \frac{\Delta(L(f))}{(L(f)-a)(L(f)-b)}.$$

Integrating we have,

$$\frac{f-a}{f-b} = c_1 \frac{L(f)-a}{L(f)-b}, \quad (3.9)$$

where c_1 is a constant. Based on equation (3.9), we can conclude that $T(r, f) = T(r, L(f)) + S(r, f)$. Clearly $c_1 = 1$ implies $f = L(f)$. Now if $c_1 \neq 1$, then from (3.9) we have

$$(1 - c_1)fL(f) + ab(1 - c_1) = (a - c_1b)L(f) + (b - c_1a)f, \quad (3.10)$$

which implies $N(r, f) = S(r, f)$. Furthermore, based on equation (3.9), we have

$$\frac{2f-a-b}{b-a} = \frac{(1+c_1)L(f)-c_1a-b}{(c_1-1)L(f)-c_1a+b}. \quad (3.11)$$

Since $N(r, f) = S(r, f)$, therefore, based on equation (3.11), it is necessary for us to have

$$N\left(r, \frac{1}{\frac{L(f)-c_1a-b}{c_1-1}}\right) = S(r, f).$$

Using the second fundamental theorem we have

$$2T(r, L(f)) \leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-b}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\frac{L(f)-c_1a-b}{c_1-1}}\right) + \bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \quad (3.12)$$

$$\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-L(f)}\right) + S(r, f)$$

$$\leq T(r, f - L(f)) + S(r, f) \leq T(r, f) + S(r, f).$$

Now from (3.12) and $T(r, f) = T(r, L(f)) + S(r, f)$ implies $T(r, f) = S(r, f)$, a contradiction.

Case 2: $\phi - \chi \neq 0$. It is easy to check

$$\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) \leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\phi-\chi}\right) \leq T(r, \phi - \chi), \quad (3.13)$$

$$\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) \leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\kappa-1}\right) \leq T(r, \kappa) + S(r, f). \quad (3.14)$$

Using (3.13), (3.14), (3.7) and (3.8) from (3.2) we get

$$T(r, f) \leq 2m\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + (3k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \quad (3.15)$$

Three cases are listed below and will be discussed next.

Case-2.1: If $a^{(k)} \neq a, b$, then from (3.15) we have

$$\begin{aligned} T(r, f) &\leq 2m\left(r, \frac{L(f)-a^{(k)}}{f-a}\right) + 2m\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a^{(k)}}\right) + (3k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq 2T(r, L(f)) - 2N\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a^{(k)}}\right) + (3k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-b}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a^{(k)}}\right) \\ &\quad + (3k+3)\bar{N}(r, f) - 2N\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a^{(k)}}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-L(f)}\right) + (3k+3)\bar{N}(r, f) - N\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a^{(k)}}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq T(r, f) + (4k+3)\bar{N}(r, f) - N\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a^{(k)}}\right) + S(r, f). \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

(3.16) provides,

$$N\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a^{(k)}}\right) \leq (4k+3)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \quad (3.17)$$

Referring back to equation (3.17) and Lemma 2.2, it is necessary for $T\left(r, \frac{1}{\kappa}\right) = T(r, \kappa) + O(1) = S(r, f)$ to be present.

Alternatively, based on the provided condition, we can deduce that

$$T(r, f) \leq 2T(r, L(f)) + \bar{N}(r, f) \leq (22k+6)\bar{N}(r, f) < \frac{22k+6}{22k+20}T(r, f),$$

a contradiction. Then from (3.14), we have $\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) \leq S(r, f)$. Hence from $T(r, \kappa) = S(r, f)$ we have $N(r, \kappa) = k\bar{N}(r, f) = S(r, f)$. By proceeding as in (3.8) and (3.7), we obtain

$$T(r, \phi - \chi) = S(r, f). \quad (3.18)$$

Using (3.18), from (3.13), (3.14) and (3.2) we get $T(r, f) = S(r, f)$, a contradiction.

Case-2.2: If $a^{(k)} \equiv a$, then we have $m(r, \kappa) = m\left(r, \frac{L(f)-a^{(k)}}{f-a}\right) = S(r, f)$. Next dealing in the same way as done in (3.8) we have

$$m(r, \chi) \leq K\bar{N}(r, f). \quad (3.19)$$

Using (3.19), (3.14), (3.13), (3.7) and (3.2) we get

$$T(r, f) \leq (3k+2)\bar{N}(r, f),$$

a contradiction.

Case-2.3. If $a^{(k)} \equiv b$, from (3.2), (3.13) and (3.7), (3.8) we have

$$T(r, f) \leq m\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) + (2k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \quad (3.20)$$

$$\leq m\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-b}\right) + (2k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f)$$

$$\leq T(r, L(f)) + (2k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f).$$

(3.20) yields

$$T(r, f) + T(r, L(f)) \leq 2T(r, L(f)) + (2k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) \quad (3.21)$$

$$\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-b}\right) + \bar{N}(r, f) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-c}\right) + (2k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f)$$

$$\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-L(f)}\right) + T\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-c}\right) + (2k+3)\bar{N}(r, f) - m\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-c}\right) + S(r, f)$$

$$\leq T(r, f) + T(r, L(f)) + (3k+3)\bar{N}(r, f) - m\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-c}\right) + S(r, f),$$

where $c \neq a, b$. Immediately from (3.12), we have

$$m\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-c}\right) \leq (3k+3)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \quad (3.22)$$

Next, considering (3.20) and (3.22), we have

$$m\left(r, \frac{f-c}{L(f)-c}\right) \leq m\left(r, \frac{f}{L(f)-c}\right) + (3k+3)\bar{N}(r, f) \quad (3.23)$$

$$\leq T\left(r, \frac{L(f)-c}{f}\right) - N\left(r, \frac{f}{L(f)-c}\right) + (3k+3)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f)$$

$$\leq m\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) + N\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) - N\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-c}\right) + (4k+3)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f)$$

$$\leq T\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) - T\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-c}\right) + (7k+6)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f)$$

$$\leq (9k + 8)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f).$$

(3.6) can be expressed as

$$\chi = \left(\frac{a-c}{a-b} \cdot \frac{\Delta(L(f))}{L(f)-a} - \frac{b-c}{a-b} \cdot \frac{\Delta(L(f))}{L(f)-b} \right) \left(\frac{f-c}{L(f)-c} - 1 \right). \quad (3.24)$$

Clearly from (3.23) and (3.24) we have

$$m(r, \chi) \leq (9k + 8)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \quad (3.25)$$

So using (3.25), (3.7), (3.13) and (3.2), (3.20) we have

$$T(r, f) \leq \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) + (10k + 10)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \quad (3.26)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-b}\right) + (10k + 10)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq T\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a^{(k)}}\right) - m\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a^{(k)}}\right) + (10k + 10)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq T(r, f) - m\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a^{(k)}}\right) + (11k + 10)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we possess

$$m\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a^{(k)}}\right) \leq (11k + 10)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \quad (3.27)$$

Again using (3.26) and (3.27), we may have

$$T(r, f) \leq \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) + (10k + 10)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \quad (3.28)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{k-1}\right) + 10(k + 1)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq m\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + (11k + 10)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq m\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a^{(k)}}\right) + (11k + 10)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq (22k + 20)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \end{aligned}$$

Since the equation (3.28) leads to a contradiction, it follows that $f \equiv L(f)$.

Proof of Theorem 1.2 Here it is given that $f - a$ and $L(f) - a$ share (0,1) and $f - b$ and $L(f) - b$ share (0,1). Let's first suppose $f \not\equiv L(f)$. Then clearly from Case-1 of Theorem (1.1), we have ϕ, χ are given by (3.5), (3.6). Applying the second fundamental theorem for small functions, we obtain,

$$T(r, f) \leq \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) + \overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \quad (3.29)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \overline{N}_{(1,1)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + \overline{N}_{(1,1)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) + \sum_{p \geq 2, q \geq 2} \overline{N}_{(p,q)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + \overline{N}_{(p,q)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) + \overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\phi-\chi}\right) + \overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq T(r, \phi - \chi) + \overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq m(r, \phi) + m(r, \chi) + (k + 2)\overline{N}(r, f) \\ &\leq m\left(r, \frac{f-L(f)}{L(f)-a}\right) + (k + 2)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq m\left(r, \frac{f-a}{L(f)-a}\right) + N\left(r, \frac{f-a}{L(f)-a}\right) - N\left(r, \frac{f-a}{L(f)-a}\right) + (k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\
&\leq T\left(r, \frac{L(f)-a}{f-a}\right) - N\left(r, \frac{f-a}{L(f)-a}\right) + (k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\
&\leq m\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + N\left(r, \frac{L(f)-a}{f-a}\right) - N\left(r, \frac{f-a}{L(f)-a}\right) + (k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\
&\leq \\
&m\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + N\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + N(r, L(f) - a) - N\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a}\right) - N(r, f - a) + (k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\
&\leq T\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) - \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a}\right) + (2k+2)\bar{N}(r, f).
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, based on equation (3.29), we obtain

$$\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) = \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a}\right) \leq (2k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \quad (3.30)$$

Following exactly the procedure outlined in (3.29), we will obtain

$$\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) = \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-b}\right) \leq (2k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \quad (3.31)$$

Considering the second fundamental theorem and equations (3.30) and (3.31), we obtain

$$T(r, f) \leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) + \bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \quad (3.32)$$

$$\leq (4k+5)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) < T(r, f) + S(r, f).$$

As (3.32) contradicts the given condition. Therefore $f \equiv L(f)$.

Proof of Theorem 1.3 First let us assume $f \not\equiv L(f)$. Here it is given that $f - a$, $L(f) - a$ share $(0,1)$ and $f - b$, $L(f) - b$ share $(0,0)$. Now let us again choose the same function κ , as in the proof of Theorem 2.1. As $f - a$ and $L(f) - a$ share $(0,1)$ it follows that if z_0 is a zero of $f - a$ of multiplicity > 1 , then it is a zero of $L(f) - a$ of multiplicity > 1 .

Again,

$$\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a} \mid \geq 2\right) = \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a} \mid \geq 2\right) \quad (3.33)$$

$$\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\phi}\right) \leq (k+1)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f).$$

It follows immediately,

$$\bar{N}(r, \kappa) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\kappa}\right) \leq (k+1)\bar{N}(r, f) + k\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \quad (3.34)$$

If z_0 is a zero of $f - b$ of multiplicity $> k$, then it becomes a zero of $b^{(k)} - b$. Here if $b^{(k)} - b \not\equiv 0$, then we have $\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b} \mid \geq k+1\right) = S(r, f)$. If $b^{(k)} - b \equiv 0$, then clearly,

$$\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b} \mid \geq k+2\right) \leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\phi}\right) \leq (k+1)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f).$$

First let us consider the following function

$$\sigma = \frac{(L(f))' - a'}{L(f) - a} - \frac{f' - a'}{f - a}. \quad (3.35)$$

From (3.35), it is evident that we have

$$T(r, \sigma) = m(r, \sigma) + N(r, \sigma) \quad (3.36)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \bar{N}_* \left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}; \frac{1}{L(f)-a} \right) + \bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \bar{N} \left(r, \frac{1}{f-a} \mid \geq 2 \right) + \bar{N}(r, f) \\ &\leq (k+2)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \end{aligned}$$

Based on equation (3.5), we can conclude that

$$\phi = \frac{\Delta(f)}{f-b} \left(1 - \frac{L(f)-a}{f-a} \right),$$

i.e.,

$$\phi \frac{f-b}{\Delta(f)} = 1 - \kappa. \quad (3.37)$$

Differentiating (3.37) we get

$$\phi' \frac{f-b}{\Delta(f)} + \phi \frac{(f'-b')}{\Delta(f)} - \phi \frac{f-b}{\Delta(f)} \frac{\Delta(f)'}{\Delta(f)} = -\kappa\sigma = \left(\phi \frac{f-b}{\Delta(f)} - 1 \right) \sigma, \quad (3.38)$$

i.e.,

$$\phi' + \phi \frac{(f'-b')}{f-b} - \phi \frac{\Delta(f)'}{\Delta(f)} - \phi\sigma + \frac{\Delta(f)}{f-b}\sigma = 0, \quad (3.39)$$

$$\phi' - \phi \frac{\Delta(f)'}{\Delta(f)} - \phi\sigma + \frac{f'-b'}{f-b}(\phi - (b-a)\sigma) + (b'-a')\sigma = 0.$$

Next we are going to discuss the following two cases, which are explained below.

Case-1. $\phi - (b-a)\sigma \not\equiv 0$. From the discussion above, it is evident that we have

$$\bar{N} \left(r, \frac{1}{f-b} \right) = \sum_{p=1}^{k+2} \bar{N}_{(p,1)} \left(r, \frac{1}{f-b} \right) + \sum_{q=2}^{\infty} \bar{N}_{(1,q)} \left(r, \frac{1}{f-b} \right) + \sum_{p,q \geq 2} \bar{N}_{(p,q)} \left(r, \frac{1}{f-b} \right) \quad (3.40)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \sum_{p=0}^{k+2} \bar{N} \left(r, \frac{1}{(\phi-p(b-a)\sigma)} \right) \\ &\leq \sum_{p=0}^{k+2} T(r, (\phi-p(b-a)\sigma)) \\ &\leq 2(k+1)(k+3)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \end{aligned}$$

Considering equation (3.40) and applying the second fundamental theorem, we obtain

$$T(r, f) \leq \bar{N} \left(r, \frac{1}{f-a} \right) + \bar{N} \left(r, \frac{1}{f-b} \right) + \bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \quad (3.41)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \bar{N} \left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a} \right) + 2(k+1)(k+3)\bar{N}(r, f) + \bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq T(r, L(f)) + (2(k+1)(k+3) + 1)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \end{aligned}$$

By using (3.41) and following the exact same steps as in (3.21) – (3.25), we can obtain $m(r, \chi) \leq (6k^2 + 27k + 23)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f)$. Then using (3.13), (3.40) we can obtain from (3.2), $T(r, f) \leq (8k^2 + 36k + 31)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f)$, a contradiction. Clearly $\phi \not\equiv 0$ and from the assumption $\phi - (b-a)\sigma \not\equiv 0$, we can conclude that at least one of $\phi - p(b-a)\sigma \equiv 0$ for some $1 < p \leq k+2$. With the help of $\phi - p(b-a)\sigma \equiv 0$ from (3.39) we have

$$\frac{\phi'}{\phi} - \frac{\Delta(f)'}{\Delta(f)} - \sigma + \left(1 - \frac{1}{p} \right) \frac{f'-b'}{f-b} + \frac{1}{p} \frac{b'-a'}{b-a} \equiv 0. \quad (3.42)$$

Integrating (3.42) we have

$$(f - b)^{p-1}(b - a) = c \frac{(L(f)-a)^p}{(f-a)^p} \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta(f)}{\phi}\right)^p \tag{3.43}$$

$$= c \left(\frac{(f-b)(L(f)-a)}{f-L(f)}\right)^p.$$

Hence we get

$$f - b = \frac{b-a}{c} \left(\frac{f-L(f)}{L(f)-a}\right)^p = \frac{b-a}{c} \left(\frac{1-\kappa}{\kappa}\right)^p = \frac{b-a}{c} \left(\frac{1}{\kappa} - 1\right)^p, \tag{3.44}$$

where c is integrating constant. By (3.1) we immediately get

$$L(f) - b = (b - a)\kappa \left(\frac{1}{\kappa} - 1\right) \left(\frac{1}{c} \left(\frac{1}{\kappa} - 1\right)^{p-1} - 1\right) \tag{3.45}$$

$$= (b - a)\kappa \left(\frac{1}{\kappa} - 1\right) \left(\frac{(-1)^{p-1}}{c} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\kappa}\right)^{p-1} - 1\right).$$

Subcase-1.1: If $c = (-1)^{p-1}$, then from (3.44), (3.45) we get

$$f - b = -(b - a) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\kappa}\right)^p,$$

$$L(f) - b = (b - a)\kappa \left(\frac{1}{\kappa} - 1\right) \left(\left(1 - \frac{1}{\kappa}\right)^{p-1} - 1\right).$$

Since $f - b$ and $L(f) - b$ share 0, then clearly $\left(\left(1 - \frac{1}{\kappa}\right)^{p-1} - 1\right)$ has all exceptional values that is κ must have $p - 2$

exceptional values. Here $p < 5$, since otherwise f reduces to a constant. Now for $p > 2$ we will get $\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\kappa\left(\frac{1}{\kappa}-1\right)^{p-1}-\kappa}\right) = S(r, f)$,

which implies $T(r, \kappa) \leq (2k + 1)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f)$ and hence from (3.44) we will have

$$T(r, f) \leq pT(r, \kappa) + S(r, f) \leq 4(2k + 1)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f),$$

a contradiction. For the case $p = 2$, we get $f - b = -(b - a) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\kappa}\right)^2$ and $L(f) - b = (b - a) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\kappa}\right)$. Hence we get $T(r, f) = 2T(r, \kappa) + S(r, f)$ and $T(r, L(f)) = 2T(r, \kappa) + S(r, f)$. From the construction of κ it is easy to verify

$$s\bar{N}(r, f) + \bar{N}_L\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + \bar{N}_L\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a}\right) \leq \bar{N}(r, \kappa) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\kappa}\right).$$

Let z_0 be a pole of f and hence a pole of κ . Then from $f - b = -(b - a) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\kappa}\right)^2$ we have z_0 is a pole of $b - a$. Again let z_1 be a zero of $f - a(L(f) - a)$ of multiplicity $p(q)$. Now if $p > q$, then z_1 is a pole of κ and from $L(f) - b = (b - a) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\kappa}\right)$ we have z_1 is a zero of $a - b$. Also if $p < q$, then z_1 is a zero of κ and from the same relation we can get z_1 is either a zero of $b - a$ or $\frac{1}{b-a}$. Based on the previous discussion, it can be concluded that if z_0 and z_1 are arbitrary, then it is necessary for us to have

$$\bar{N}(r, f) + \bar{N}_*\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}; \frac{1}{L(f)-a}\right) \leq \bar{N}(r, \kappa) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\kappa}\right) \tag{3.46}$$

$$\leq \bar{N}(r, b - a) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{b-a}\right) = S(r, f).$$

Hence, from (3.46), (3.36), we obtain $T(r, \sigma) = S(r, f)$ and $\frac{\kappa'}{\kappa} = \sigma$, implies κ is a transcendental function. According to Lemma 2.3, it is necessary for us to have

$$T(r, \kappa) + S(r, f) = T(r, L(f)) = T(r, f) + S(r, f) = 2T(r, \kappa) + S(r, f),$$

this implies $T(r, \kappa) = S(r, f)$, again a contradiction.

Subcase-1.2. If $c \neq (-1)^{p-1}$, therefore, based on equations (3.44) and (3.45), it is necessary to conclude that

$$\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\kappa\left(\frac{1}{c}\left(\frac{1}{\kappa}-1\right)^{p-1}-1\right)}\right) = S(r, f) \text{ and } p < 3.$$

Then finally we have $T(r, \kappa) \leq (2k+1)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f)$ and we will have $T(r, f) \leq 3(2k+1)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f)$, again a contradiction.

Case-2. Let $\phi - (b-a)\sigma \equiv 0$. Then from (3.39) we have

$$\frac{\phi'}{\phi} - \frac{\Delta'(f)}{\Delta(f)} - \sigma - \frac{b'-a'}{b-a} = 0, \quad (3.47)$$

which on integration yields

$$\frac{f-L(f)}{(L(f)-a)(f-b)} = \frac{c}{(b-a)}. \quad (3.48)$$

Therefore clearly we can get

$$\bar{N}(r, f) = S(r, f), \quad (3.49)$$

$$\bar{N}_*\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}; \frac{1}{L(f)-a}\right) = \bar{N}_*\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}; \frac{1}{L(f)-b}\right) = S(r, f).$$

Using (3.49) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) &\leq \bar{N}_{(1,1)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) + \bar{N}_{(1,1)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) + \sum_{p \geq 2} \bar{N}_{(p,p)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a}\right) \\ &+ \sum_{p \geq 2} \bar{N}_{(p,p)}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\phi-\chi}\right) + S(r, f). \end{aligned}$$

Next proceeding exactly in the same manner as done in (3.29) – (3.32) of Theorem 2.2, we can get a contradiction again.

Proof of Theorem 1.4

It is given that f and $L(f)$ share $(0, \infty)$, therefore 0 must be an exceptional value of both f and $L(f)$. Next consider the function

$$\mu = \frac{L(f)}{f}. \quad (3.50)$$

Applying the second fundamental theorem, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} T(r, f) &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) + \bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\mu-1}\right) + \bar{N}(r, f) \leq T(r, \mu) + \bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq (k+1)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) < T(r, f), \end{aligned}$$

a contradiction. Hence the result follows.

Proof of Theorem 1.5

First let us assume that $f \not\equiv L(f)$. It is given that f and $L(f)$ share $(0, k)$ and $f - b, L(f) - b$ share $(0, 0)$. Now clearly from the property of weighted sharing, the zeros of f must have multiplicity $\geq 2k + 1$ and the zeros of $L(f)$ have multiplicity $k + 1 \geq 2$.

Considering the function μ as defined in (3.50) we can construct the following function

$$\psi = \frac{(f'(f-b) - f'(f'-b'))(f-L(f))}{f(f-b)}.$$

It is easy to verify that $k\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) \leq N\left(r, \frac{1}{\psi}\right) \leq (k+1)\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f)$. Using the second fundamental theorem we have,

$$\begin{aligned} T(r, f) &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) + \bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\mu-1}\right) + \bar{N}(r, f) \\ &\leq T(r, \mu) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) + \bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \frac{(k+1)^2}{k}\bar{N}(r, f) + (k+1)\bar{N}(r, f) \\ &\leq \frac{(k+1)(2k+1)}{k}\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) < T(r, f), \end{aligned}$$

a contradiction. Again if $\psi \equiv 0$, then we will have $T(r, f) = S(r, f)$ which leads a contradiction again. Hence $f \equiv L(f)$.

Proof of Theorem 1.6

It is given that f and $L(f)$ share $(0, k)$ and $f - b$, $L(f) - b$ share $(0, 1)$. It is given that $k \geq 2$. As f and $L(f)$ share the values $(0, k)$, it follows that the zeros of f are of multiplicity $\geq 2k + 1$. Now let us denote the function,

$$\gamma = \frac{L(f)'}{L(f)} - \frac{f'}{f},$$

$$\delta = \frac{L(f)' - b'}{L(f) - b} - \frac{f' - b'}{f - b}.$$

If $\delta \equiv 0$, then we have $L(f) - b = c(f - b)$ for some constant c . This implies $f - b$ and $L(f) - b$ share $(0, \infty)$ and $N(r, f) = S(r, f)$ then clearly from Theorem H we will get $f \equiv L(f)$. Similarly if $\gamma \equiv 0$, then we will also get $f \equiv L(f)$. So we can assume $\delta \not\equiv 0$ and $\gamma \not\equiv 0$. Since f and $L(f)$ share $(0, k)$, it follows that the zeros of f are of multiplicities $2k + 1$ and that of $L(f)$ are of multiplicity $k(\geq 2)$. Therefore we must have,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f} \mid \geq k+1\right) &\leq \frac{1}{k}N\left(r, \frac{1}{\delta}\right) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{k}\left\{\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b} \mid \geq 2\right) + \bar{N}(r, f)\right\} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{k}N\left(r, \frac{1}{\gamma}\right) + \frac{1}{k}\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{k}\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f} \mid \geq k+1\right) + \frac{2}{k}\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f), \end{aligned}$$

i.e.,

$$\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f} \mid \geq k+1\right) \leq \frac{2}{k-1}\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \quad (3.51)$$

From (3.50) it is clear that,

$$\bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) \leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f} \mid \geq k+1\right) + k\bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f). \quad (3.52)$$

Next from the second fundamental theorem and (3.51), (3.52) we get

$$T(r, f) \leq \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) + \bar{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b}\right) + \bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \quad (3.53)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \frac{2+2k}{k-1}\bar{N}(r, f) + (k+1)\bar{N}(r, f) \\ &= \frac{(k+1)^2}{k-1}\bar{N}(r, f) \end{aligned}$$

$$< T(r, f) + S(r, f).$$

As (3.53) gives a contradiction, we have $f \equiv L(f)$.

Proof of Theorem 1.7

It is given that $f - a, L(f) - a$ share $(0, k)$ and $f - b, L(f) - b$ share $(0, k)$. Since a, b be two non-zero rationals, clearly we have

$$\overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a} \mid \geq k+1\right) = \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a} \mid \geq k+1\right) = S(r, f),$$

$$\overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b} \mid \geq k+1\right) = \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-b} \mid \geq k+1\right) = S(r, f).$$

Let us consider the following functions

$$\alpha = \frac{f-a}{L(f)-a}, \beta = \frac{f-b}{L(f)-b}.$$

Here we have,

$$\tau = \frac{\alpha}{\beta} = \frac{(f-a)(L(f)-b)}{(L(f)-a)(f-b)}.$$

It is easy to check,

$$\overline{N}\left(r, \frac{\alpha}{\beta}\right) + \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{\beta}{\alpha}\right) \leq \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-a} \mid \geq k+1\right) + \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{f-b} \mid \geq k+1\right) = S(r, f). \quad (3.54)$$

Now using (3.54), we have

$$T(r, \tau) \leq \overline{N}(r, \tau) + \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\tau}\right) + \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\tau-1}\right) \leq \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\tau-1}\right) + S(r, f) \quad (3.55)$$

$$\leq N\left(r, \frac{1}{\tau-1}\right) + S(r, f) \leq T(r, \tau) + S(r, f).$$

Clearly from 3.55 we have $T(r, \tau) = N\left(r, \frac{1}{\tau-1}\right) + S(r, f) = \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{\tau-1}\right) + S(r, f)$ and hence $m\left(r, \frac{1}{\tau-1}\right) = S(r, f)$. Again we have

$$\frac{ab}{f^2} = \frac{a-b}{\tau-1} \left(1 - \frac{L(f)}{f}\right) \frac{1}{f} + \frac{a}{f} + \frac{L(f)}{f} \left(\frac{b}{f} - 1\right) \quad (3.56)$$

$$= \frac{1}{f} \left(\frac{a-b}{\tau-1} \left(1 - \frac{L(f)}{f}\right) + a + b \frac{L(f)}{f}\right) - \frac{L(f)}{f}.$$

From (3.56) we have $m\left(r, \frac{1}{f}\right) = S(r, f)$ and hence $m(r, L(f)) = S(r, f)$. Now

$$\Delta = \frac{\tau'}{\tau} = \frac{f'-a'}{f-a} - \frac{f'-b'}{f-b} + \frac{L(f)'}{L(f)-b} - \frac{L(f)'}{L(f)-a}. \quad (3.57)$$

It is easy to verify

$$N(r, f) - \overline{N}(r, f) \leq N\left(r, \frac{1}{\Delta}\right) \leq T(r, \Delta) + S(r, f) = S(r, f),$$

and hence $N(r, f) \leq \overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f)$ and hence $N(r, f) = \overline{N}(r, f)$. From above we have $T(r, L(f)) = m(r, L(f)) + N(r, L(f)) = (k+1)\overline{N}(r, f)$. Using this and the second main theorem we get

$$\begin{aligned} T(r, f) &\leq \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-a}\right) + \overline{N}\left(r, \frac{1}{L(f)-b}\right) + \overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq 2T(r, L(f)) + \overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f) \\ &\leq (2k+3)\overline{N}(r, f) + S(r, f), \end{aligned}$$

a contradiction. If $\Delta \equiv 0$, then integrating from (3.57) we have $\frac{f-a}{f-b} = c_1 \frac{L(f)-a}{L(f)-b}$, where c_1 is a constant. If $c_1 \neq 1$, then clearly from this relation we get $N(r, f) = S(r, f)$. Now we have $T(r, L(f)) = N(r, L(f)) + S(r, f) = S(r, f)$ and this implies $T(r, f) = S(r, f)$, a contradiction.

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